

Procedure :

Dilute 5 ml (0.1 M) nickel ion solution to 10 ml with distilled water. Add 4 ml of buffer solution (6.8 pH) and 1 ml (0.02M) indicator. Titrate with (0.02M) hippuric acid until colour change from red to yellow. Blank was also run for better results.

References

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Direct Estimation of Zinc in Complex Materials

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ZINC belongs to the more common trace elements. Its average concentration in the lithosphere is in the order of 60-70 p.p.m. It mostly occurs as the sulfide, sphalerite, ZnS, but the carbonate smithsonite ZnCO₃ and the silicate willemite Zn₂(SiO₄) are also common zinc minerals. The occurrence of zinc in silicate rocks was examined by Sandell and Goldich who found that the amounts of zinc present in rocks of the plutonic and volcanic series could be related to the sum of the magnesium and ferrous iron, and also to the manganese content. Rader has also shown that the zinc content of basaltic rocks can be related to the total iron content. In metallurgical products particularly in the non-ferrous field zinc is often encountered and its analysis called for, except where it is one of the principal constituents, as in brass (Zn, Cu) German Silver (Zn, Cu, Ni) and in die casting alloys (Zn, Cu, Al) where it is commonly reported by difference. Granulated zinc is a necessary substance in the chemical laboratory. Its resistance to rusting makes zinc valuable as a protective coating on iron surfaces (galvanized iron). Considerable quantities of zinc are used as anodes in electrical batteries. The ZnO is used as a pigment and chemical in rubber goods, including automobile tyres and extensively as a paint pigment. It is used in glazes, in enamels, as an ointment, as dusting powder etc. The chloride is used as a preservative of wood. The sulfide is a valuable white pigment, with barium sulphate it forms lithopone. Recently zinc has been shown to be necessary to the growth

of plants, certain chemical glasswares contain from 3-11% zinc. Zinc determination should not be made in these wares.

The quantitative estimation of zinc in a complex material, where it is associated with, Cu, Pb, Al, Fe, Mg, Ca, Cd etc. is a tedious process. The gravimetric methods are quite lengthy, because the separation of each group is required before reaching the IV group (Zn, Ni, Co, etc. comes in fourth group) and also during the precipitation of zinc with diammonium hydrogen phosphate magnesium interferes. In the volumetric analysis zinc can be titrated with EDTA using Eriochrome Black T at pH 10 but in the presence of Mg this method proved futile.

Zinc at pH 6 forms coloured complex with xylenol orange (red complex). When it is titrated with standard EDTA, the colour change at the equivalence point is from red to yellow. This method has successfully been applied for the estimation of zinc present in rock and minerals where it is generally associated with several elements viz. Cu, Pb, Al, Fe, Mg, Ca and Cd etc.

In the proposed method Pb has been removed as PbSO₄ and filtered off alongwith silica. Iron has also been removed as iron-hydroxide by precipitating it with NaOH, copper and aluminium is complexed with sodium thiosulphate and sodium fluoride respectively and zinc is titrated directly with standard 0.01M EDTA at pH 6 (which was maintained using hexamine) using 0.5% xylenol orange as indicator. The colour change at the end point is from red to yellow. Magnesium and calcium do not interfere at pH 6.

Reagents :

1-EDTA : 0.01M—3.7225 gms of EDTA was weighed and dissolved in one litre of distilled water.

2-Sodium thiosulphate—10% soln. 10 gms of sodium thiosulphate was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water.

3-Sodium fluoride 5% solution—5 gms sodium fluoride was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water.

4-Hexamine—It is used as buffer to maintain pH 6.

5-Xylenol orange 0.5% (0.5 gms) of the reagent was weighed, dissolved in little alcohol and was made upto 100 ml by distilled water.

Experimental

Several samples of zinc were weighed. The samples were decomposed by 1 : 2 HNO₃ and

evaporated nearly to dryness. To this 2-3 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 was added, and the solution was evaporated on a hot plate to fumes of sulphur trioxide in order to expel nitric acid. The presence of even a small quantity of NO_3 ions increases the solubility of the lead sulphate. The residual liquid is treated with 50 ml of distilled water and the insoluble lead sulphate alongwith silica is filtered of after digesting the solution. The filtrate so obtained is made upto 100 ml in volumetric flasks. 20 ml of the solution was taken out by a pipette in a beaker. To this solution 50 ml of distilled water was added, and the solution was heated. To the hot solution 5% solution of NaOH was added, dropwise to precipitate iron as $Fe(OH)_3$, aluminium goes into solution as sodium aluminate, Cu and Zn also remain in the solution $Fe(OH)_3$ was filtered off. The filtrate was then acidified with dil HCl. To this solution 2 ml of 10% sodium thiosulphate was added to complex copper ions and 2 ml of 5% sodium fluoride was added to complex aluminium ions, 2-3 drops of xylenol orange was added, then solid hexamine was added with agitation until the colour of the solution becomes red (pH 6). The solution was titrated with 0.01M EDTA until the colour changes from red to yellow. The reading was noted and the percentage of zinc in the samples was calculated.

By Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer :

For the estimation of zinc by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer a standard calibration graph was prepared. The absorbances were noted against known concentration of zinc. The unknown samples of zinc were then run through the instrument and the absorbances were noted. By interpolating the values in the standard graph the percentage of Zn was determined.

The results obtained by this method have been compared successfully with those obtained by instrumental method i.e. the samples were run on Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer and the results are given in the Table :

Percentage of Zn		
	By A.A.S.	Proposed method
1.	1.10	1.05
2.	0.50	0.42
3.	10.00	9.75
4.	3.20	3.10
5.	6.00	5.60
6.	0.30	0.12
7.	00.50	0.37
8.	1.20	0.99
9.	5.20	4.97
10.	4.36	4.06

Results and Discussion

Xylenol orange forms complex with zinc at pH 6 which was maintained by Hexaine (Hexamethylene

tetramine) but the Zn-EDTA complex is more stable than dye-Zn complex and at the equivalence point all the zinc ions are complexed with EDTA and the xylenol orange dye remains in the solution which is yellow in colour. Copper and aluminium do not interfere as they have already been complexed with sodium thiosulphate and sodium fluoride respectively. Magnesium and calcium also do not interfere as they do not form complex at pH 6.

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Photometric Study of Uranyl-Terramycin Complex*

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THE spectrophotometric investigation of uranyl-terramycin complex in solution has been studied photometrically at pH 1.3. The composition of the complex is established by Job's and Slope ratio methods as 1 : 1. The stability constant calculated from the data obtained in Job's method is 1.9×10^9 . Beer's law is obeyed.

A survey of literature has revealed that much work has not been done on the "Metal complexes of antibiotics" particularly of terramycin. Metal complexes of streptomycin have been studied by Foye and Lange¹ and Zahn and Eisenbrandt². Uranyl-streptomycin complex has been recently studied spectrophotometrically by Agarwal *et al*³. The spectrophotometric investigation of uranyl-terramycin complex has been carried out and results are communicated here.

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